

The Numismatic Chronicle 171 Offprint

Nero and the Making of the Roman Medallion

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LONDON
THE ROYAL NUMISMATIC SOCIETY
2011

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[PLATES 10-13]

THE PURPOSE of this paper is to present and discuss an *as* of the Roman emperor Nero (AD 54–68) which, even if rather inconspicuous at first sight, might add to our understanding of the development of special issues in the Roman principate.

As (orichalcum)

Obv. NERO CLAVD CAESAR AVG GER P M TR P IM[P P] P

[Radiate head of Nero to the right.]

Rev. GENIO – [A]VGVSTI, S – C (in left and right fields), I (in exergue)

Genius standing left, cloak around waist, holding *cornucopiae* in his left hand, sacrificing with the right hand out of *patera* over lighted altar.

Weight 7.05 g; die axis 6 h; maximum diameter 26 mm; holed (from the obverse) at 5 h (obv.)

Private collection. **Plate 10, 1** and **1a** (2 x).

Mint of Rome, c. AD 64

RIC 1 (second ed.), 215

MacDowall² 276 (Issue III: AD 64)

BMCRE 1, 251

BNCMER 2, 328f.

A specimen struck from the same reverse die is in the collection of the American Numismatic Society in New York (inv. no. 1892.32.1, 8.55 g, 6 h: **Pl. 10, 2**), another was offered in the auction *Ars Classica* 17 (3 Oct. 1934: Sir Arthur J. Evans et al.), no. 1275 (8.78 g: **Pl. 10, 3**). These two coins clearly come from two different obverse dies, and the coin presented here from a third; despite this, we can be sure that it originally featured Nero's head with a radiate crown on the obverse, of which only the faintest traces are still to be seen. There are no indications whatsoever that we are dealing with a modern forgery; the coin does not display any traces of casting.

¹ The authors are indebted to Richard Abdy (London), Karsten Dahmen (Berlin), Ben Lee Damsky (Decatur, AL), Kay Ehling (Munich), Volker Heuchert (Oxford) and especially to Klaus Vondrovec (Vienna) for their assistance in preparing this article. BEW would like to thank the American Numismatic Society (New York) and the Department of Coins and Medals of the Fitzwilliam Museum (Cambridge) for hosting him as Visiting Scholar in Residence in the summer of 2010 and the academic year 2010/2011 respectively, thereby enabling *inter alia* research work for this contribution. His research fellowship at the University of Cambridge was generously funded by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF, project no. J 2993).

² D.W. MacDowall, *The Western Coinages of Nero* [=WCN]. Numismatic Notes and Monographs 161 (New York, 1979).

The piece is remarkable in that the emperor's portrait is largely missing, and this is indeed why we believe it worth publication. Whereas no details of Nero's features survive, the basic outlines of his head are still clearly visible. In the centre of the obverse field, a circle which is not perfectly round and which has a diameter of 16 to 17 mm can be seen. Inside this circle, the surface recedes by some 0.3 mm compared with the lowest layer of the outside areas. These areas still display most of the obverse legend; also the lower part of the truncation is still visible. Whereas the coin generally shows a brownish patination over the original brass colour, on the faint traces of Nero's head in the centre some spots of reddish colour can be seen. The specimen was subjected to a metallurgical analysis by μ -RFA in Vienna in June 2010, the results of which will be published in detail elsewhere.³ They indicate that the coin as such is of orichalcum, as expected, but that the zinc content of the metal on the reddish spots is lower than elsewhere on the surface, thereby confirming the impression one gets when examining the coin with the naked eye: these are spots of copper.

What to make of this? It is clear that the emperor's portrait was not missing from the die, but that it was there, as the facial outlines which are still visible prove. Hence we need to explain why it is now no longer clearly visible on the coin. A first thought could be that we are just dealing with some kind of damage to the flan, parts of the metal having broken away or disappeared due to corrosion. In the present case, however, the easiest explanation is not the best: the edges of the inner circle are so clear-cut that one certainly cannot attribute them to corrosion, or to any operation of chance. Furthermore, if the upper layer of metal had disappeared after the striking of the coin due to some error in the production process of the flan, then no traces of the portrait would be visible. It should also be emphasized that the inner circle, even though not fully round nor perfectly centred, is much too regular to be the result of mere chance: it must be intentional.

As is well known, Nero fell victim to *damnatio memoriae*. In some cases, the consequences of an emperor's *damnatio* are to be seen on his coinage as well,⁴ and although Nero is not the best example, there are imperial and provincial coins from his reign which were disfigured or altered in various ways.⁵ Quite frequently, countermarks (of different kinds) were applied to Nero's coins in the political turmoil after his death, and sometimes they were struck right across his portrait (**Pl. 10, 4**).

³ N. Schindel – B. Woytek – B. Frühmann – M. Grießer, 'Die erste bimetallische Münze? Metallanalytische Untersuchungen an einem As des Kaisers Nero', *Technologische Studien des Kunsthistorischen Museums, Wien* 8 (2011), forthcoming. This publication also features enlarged high quality colour images of the coin.

⁴ Compare, most recently, the overviews by A. Savio, 'L'effetto della *damnatio memoriae* sulle monete dell'alto Impero', in: L. Travaini (ed.), *Valori e disvalori simbolici delle monete. I Trenta denari di Giuda*. Monete 3 (Rome, 2009), pp. 105–17, esp. 111–5 and by A. Hostein, 'Monnaie et *damnatio memoriae*: problèmes méthodologiques (I^{er}-V^e siècle après J.-C.)', *Cahiers Glotz* 15 (2004), pp. 219–36. See also R. Wolters, *Nummi Signati. Untersuchungen zur römischen Münzprägung und Geldwirtschaft*. Vestigia 49 (Munich, 1999), p. 317 with note 260, and R. Münsterberg, 'Damnatio memoriae', *Monatsblatt der Numismatischen Gesellschaft in Wien* 11, no. 5 (= no. 418 overall), May 1918, pp. 32–7, esp. 34.

⁵ The evidence has recently been summarized by E.R. Varner, *Mutilation and Transformation. Damnatio memoriae and Roman Imperial Portraiture*. Monumenta Graeca et Romana 10 (Leiden – Boston, 2004), pp. 50–1. See generally *RPC* 1, p. 53 for the relatively small scale of the measures, in a broader perspective.

This was not of course exactly a *damnatio*, but it may certainly be regarded as a related phenomenon in this case. While countermarking was a measure taken by some authority – our example being an ‘SPQR’ stamp which has plausibly been associated with the uprising of C. Iulius Vindex in Gaul or the early moves of Galba⁶ –, there are also pieces attesting attempts at a kind of *damnatio* in a grey area between the public and private sphere: Nero’s face is sometimes chiselled off or even recut, and the emperor’s name was occasionally erased from coins.⁷ There are bronze coins which show chisel marks on his face, although it is often difficult to distinguish strokes applied intentionally from fortuitous ones.⁸ Thus, one might be tempted to believe that on the newly discovered *as* Nero’s portrait was destroyed after his death, but on closer examination this hypothesis can also be ruled out. Even if we suppose that someone took the pains to gouge out the emperor’s head, this fails to explain the strange structure of the obverse as it is now: after removing the coin’s surface with a mechanical device, no trace whatsoever of the head would have remained; apart from that, no file marks or scratches are to be seen on the coin.

In our opinion, the phenomenon to be observed on the obverse of the *as* can only be explained by assuming that a small quantity of metal different from the brass of the main component of the flan had been applied to the inner circle in order to function as a kind of inlay. It seems difficult to decide how this was done, i. e. whether a small disc of metal was pressed onto the brass flan, or whether some metal was smelted onto it. Afterwards, the flan was struck, and the image on the anvil (= obverse) die was thus impressed on a two-component surface. At an unknown date after the piece’s production, the small, thin inlay got lost. Since it was certainly no thicker than about 0,2–0,3 mm (the depth of the inner circle), it is understandable that the die also left an impression on the underlying brass, even if it is of course blurred there and more indistinct than on the original surface. As for the type of metal inlay used, the reddish spots suggest that it was copper. The ancient hole might provide further evidence that the coin was, in its original state, aesthetically very appealing: it may have been affixed to a wooden structure (or something similar) with a nail in order to display the emperor’s portrait which will probably have shone in red, while being most unusually encircled by a golden halo.

⁶ See R. Martini, *Collezione Pangerl. Contromarche imperiali romane (Augustus–Vespasianus). The Pangerl Collection. Catalog and Commentary on the Countermarked Roman Imperial Coins*. Nomismata 6 (Milan, 2003), p. 67, countermark 27. On countermarking in this context, see also Varner, p. 51 with fig. 45, and C.J. Howgego, *Greek Imperial Countermarks. Studies in the Provincial Coinage of the Roman Empire*. RNS SP 17 (London, 1985), p. 6.

⁷ See L. Ruzicka, ‘Doppelte Erasion auf einer Münze des Nero von Thessalonike’, *ZfN* 34 (1924), pp. 354f.; R. Mowat, ‘Martelage et abrasion des monnaies sous l’empire Romain. Leurs contremarques’, *RN*, 4ème série, 5 (1901), pp. 443–71, pl. 10, esp. 448–50; R. Mowat, ‘Abrasion d’une contremarque de Néron’, *RN*, 4ème série, 13 (1909), pp. 500–2; M. Bernhart, ‘Erasionen’, in: *Heinrich Buchenau am 20. April 1922 60 Jahre alt* (Munich, 1922), pp. 1–8, esp. pp. 2f. (nos. 3–5), p. 7 (table) and p. 8 (erased countermark?); Th. O. Mabbott, ‘Epictetus and Nero’s Coinage’, *CIPh* 36 (1941), pp. 398–9; D. Salzmann, ‘Vespasian statt Nero – Ein numismatischer Palimpsest’, *Arch. Anz. DAI* 1984, pp. 295–9.

⁸ B. Paschke, ‘Das verunstaltete Münzportrait des Nero: Spuren einer privaten *damnatio memoriae*?’, *MÖNG* 47/1 (2007), pp. 16–24; in the case of the coin presented by him, the stroke seems to result from chance, not from intention. G.C. Boon, ‘A counterstamped and defaced *As* of Nero from Exeter’, *NC* 7th series 18 (1978), pp. 178–80, similarly misses the point.

If this explanation is accepted, we are dealing with what is left of one of the earliest bimetallic pieces in the history of Roman coinage. Since the publication of J.M.C. Toynbee's influential monograph on Roman medallions, it has been accepted among numismatists that bimetallic pieces originated under Galba (AD 68–69),⁹ a view recently confirmed by Peter Franz Mittag in his corpus of medallions and pseudo-medallions produced prior to the accession of Antoninus Pius.¹⁰ Unfortunately, Toynbee did not illustrate the one Galba specimen to which she refers, a *sestertius* on a bimetallic flan with the reverse type SPQR / OB / CIV SER in oak-wreath¹¹ in the Coin Cabinet of the Archaeological Museum of Naples.¹² Mittag was not shown the piece when he visited the Museum in Naples in preparation of his catalogue,¹³ and according to the cabinet's keeper, it is not to be found today either: all that remains is a handwritten file card (without image) indicating that a piece of the dimension and weight given by Toynbee was present in the collection in the years 1912 and 1923.¹⁴

Toynbee's data concerning the Galba piece do not, *a priori*, seem unreliable, but cannot be checked. The earliest bimetallic specimen both commonly acknowledged as such and today known at least from a photograph is a *sestertius* of Trajan (AD 98–117) with on its reverse the emperor on horseback attacking a fallen Dacian with a spear¹⁵ (Pl. 11, 5): it was reportedly struck on a composite flan consisting of a copper core and an orichalcum rim¹⁶ and may be dated to *c.* AD 105–107.¹⁷ The line of division between the two zones of the flan can clearly be discerned on the image. This piece was therefore presumably produced using a planchet of a type comparable to the flans of the vast majority of later bimetallic coins and medallions of the Roman

⁹ J.M.C. Toynbee, *Roman Medallions*. With an Introduction to the Reprint Edition by W.E. Metcalf (reprint New York, 1986; first ed. 1944), p. 26: "A pseudo medallion of Galba at Naples, with a regular sestertius and dupondius type struck on a medallion flan, appears to be our first example of a genuinely bimetallic piece: on the obverse the line of division between the two metals can be clearly seen cutting through the letters of the circumference legend".

¹⁰ P.F. Mittag, *Römische Medaillons. Caesar bis Hadrian* (Stuttgart, 2010), p. 18, note 31: "Die Technik, bimetalliche Medaillons zu fertigen, wurde in der römischen Numismatik erstmals unter Galba angewendet." See also p. 41.

¹¹ Toynbee, *Medallions*, p. 26, note 39: *RIC* 1 (first ed.) Galba 50 [= *RIC* 1 (second ed.) 262; see note 14 below].

¹² According to Toynbee p. 26, note 39, the diameter of the piece is 40 mm and the weight 47.1 g. Such a large piece is not listed among Galba's SPQR OB CIV SER bronzes by G. Fiorelli, *Catalogo del Museo Nazionale di Napoli. Medagliere. II. Monete Romane* (Naples, 1870), pp. 88f.

¹³ Cp. Mittag, *Medaillons*, p. 128, no. Galba 1: "non vidi" (see also p. 112).

¹⁴ Weight 47.20 g; diameter 40 mm. The card further says: "Ottima conservazione" and gives the reference to Cohen (second edition) no. 297 ("IMP. SER. GALBA AVG. TR. P. Son buste lauré et drapé à dr.", rev. "S.P.Q.R. OB. CIV. SER."). It does not indicate that the piece was bimetallic. Thanks are due to Teresa Giove (Naples) for providing this information.

¹⁵ The piece was first published by M. Buffagni – L. Reggiani, 'Un sestertio bimetallico o pseudo medaglione di Traiano', *RIN* 82 (1980), pp. 229–30; Mittag, *Medaillons*, no. Tra 9.

¹⁶ According to the authors, the patina of the piece (23.7 g; 35 mm) obscures the original colours of the metals ("Data la colorazione bruna che ricopre l'intera moneta non è distinguibile il colore giallo dell'oricalco dal colore rosso della parte centrale in rame.", p. 230).

¹⁷ See B. Woytek, *Die Reichsprägung des Kaisers Traianus (98–117)*. *Moneta Imperii Romani* 14, 2 vols (Vienna, 2010), no. 203cB (Abschlag).

Empire: the core of the object was a disc in the softer copper which was encircled by a rim in the harder brass.¹⁸ The production technique of bimetallic pieces in general has never been studied properly: there is some evidence that the two parts were at least sometimes joined using a tongue-and-groove joint around the edge,¹⁹ although not all the surviving central fragments of formerly bimetallic medallions show traces of this technique.²⁰ Hence the mint may occasionally have resorted to other solutions, and in particular different casting techniques may be envisaged;²¹ it is evident that more research on this topic is badly needed. Be that as it may, a nice parallel to the Trajanic *sestertius* is provided, for example, by a specimen of Caracalla's circus *sestertius* in the British Museum struck on a bimetallic flan, which was stripped of its patina and thus shows the original colours of the metals (Pl. 11, 6).²²

Bimetallic strikes from *sestertius*-, *dupondius*- or *as*-dies were, of course, never the norm, but always exceptional: as a rule, this technique was reserved for imperial medallions which frequently lack the SC.²³ The heyday of bimetallicism of this kind was the sole reign of Commodus (AD 180–192): for this emperor alone, more bimetallic medallions are attested than for all other Roman rulers put together.²⁴ The evidence for the use of bimetallic flans between Trajan and Commodus is rather patchy, and no systematic study of their occurrence has been published; a brief overview in

¹⁸ For a few exceptions to this rule (with a core in brass and a rim in copper, all from the reign of Commodus), see H. Dressel, *Die römischen Medaillone des Münzkabinetts der Staatlichen Museen zu Berlin*. Bearbeitet von Kurt Regling, 2 vols (Dublin/Zürich, 1972), p. 134, notes 1 and 2.

¹⁹ On this, see the observations by L. Michellini Tocci, *I medaglioni romani e i contornati del Medagliere Vaticano* (Città del Vaticano, 1965), pp. 251f.: he describes a fragmentary bimetallic medallion struck for Caracalla as Caesar, the inner part of which exhibited a groove at the edge. The piece was later restored, so that the edge of the core metal is no longer visible, and appeared in several auction sales: MMAG 28 (19 June 1964), 408 = Leu 25 (23 April 1980), 353 = Lanz 100 (20 Nov. 2000: Benz coll., part three), 81 (47.59 g).

²⁰ This is true, e.g., for the fragment of a small bimetallic medallion of Severus Alexander in London which has fairly flat edges (inv. no. BM 1992,0509.365).

²¹ Cp. for example J.M.C. Toynbee, 'Un nouveau médaillon de bronze de Gallienus, bi-métallique', *GNS* 10 (1960, Heft 37), pp. 3–5.

²² Inv. no. BM 1981,0412.1; weight: 33.81 g. This is the piece first published by C. Fontana, 'Un sestertio bimetallico o pseudo-medaglione di Caracalla', *RIN* 68 (1966), pp. 91–6, whose pedigree may be reconstructed as follows: Schulman 17 May 1938, 1531 = Santamaria 23 Oct. 1950 (Magnaguti coll., part four), 175 = Leu 25 (23 April 1980), 357. Fontana refers to other bimetallic *sestertii* of the Severan period on pp. 93 (Paris) and 95 (in trade: Rodolfo Ratto). The latter piece of Caracalla (rev. emperor in triumphal quadriga), from the Mazzini collection (vol. 3, Caracalla 233), reappeared in Lanz 100 (20 Nov. 2000: Benz coll., part three), 82 = Lanz 109 (27 May 2002), 601. For a bimetallic *as* of Elagabalus from the Benz coll., see Lanz 100, 134.

²³ The schematic classification of medallion SC and non-SC pieces as "medaglioni del Senato" and "medaglioni imperatorii" adopted by Francesco Gnecci – *I medaglioni romani*, 3 vols (Milan, 1912), esp. vol. 1, pp. XXXVII ff. – cannot stand, of course: on the problem of the SC for our topic in general, see Toynbee, *Medallions*, pp. 21 and 28–30, and Mittag, *Medaillons*, pp. 16–21.

²⁴ See Toynbee, *Medallions*, p. 18, note 4 (statistics based on the material known to Toynbee). See also M.R. Kaiser-Raiß, 'Ein bimetalliches Medaillon des Commodus aus Carnuntum. Römische Bronzemedallions in Carnuntum und Vindobona und ihre Funktion', *NZ* 98 (1984), pp. 27–35. On the medallions of Commodus in general, see M.R. Kaiser-Raiß, *Die stadtrömische Münzprägung während der Alleinherrschaft des Commodus. Untersuchungen zur Selbstdarstellung eines römischen Kaisers* (Frankfurt am Main, 1980), pp. 65–74 (contains valuable material, but is to be used with caution).

Toynbee's monograph²⁵ and some diligent notes by Heinrich Dressel²⁶ remain the best treatment to date. According to the evidence currently available, no bimetallic pieces proper were produced under Hadrian,²⁷ although the mint experimented with the visual effects of orichalcum medallions set in profiled copper frames under his rule.²⁸ During the reigns of Antoninus Pius and Marcus Aurelius, similar experiments continued, and under Marcus bimetallic medallions proper are also attested.²⁹ After Commodus, the frequency of the use of bimetallic flans decreased significantly, with minor concentrations to be observed under Alexander Severus (AD 222–235) and Gordian III (AD 238–244); they are attested until Diocletian.³⁰

There have, however, been two claims that bimetallic pieces existed as early as the reign of Nero. When Robert Göbl³¹ re-published an orichalcum *as* of Nero struck on a large flan with grooved borders (rev. the emperor as *Apollo citharoedus* advancing right with lyre³²: **Pl. 11, 7**), which was known to him only from its illustration in an auction catalogue,³³ he stated in his description that the flan was bimetallic and noted specifically that this had not been recognized by the cataloguer in the 1930s.³⁴ Since the piece is not available for inspection, it is impossible to decide whether Göbl was right; one of the concentric lines of the coin's rim might indeed indicate the separation of two zones of different metals, but this is far from certain. Intriguingly, this as type produced at the mint of Rome in AD 64 is part of the same issue as the coin presented here for the first time.

The second piece is of greater importance here. In general, it should be stressed that the production of what are conventionally termed "pseudo-medallions" seems to have flourished under Nero between AD 64 and 66.³⁵ In most cases, *sestertius*

²⁵ Toynbee, *Medallions*, pp. 17f.

²⁶ Dressel, *Medaillone*, pp. 132–7.

²⁷ Thus now Mittag, *Medaillons*, p. 48.

²⁸ See Mittag, *Medaillons*, no. Hadr 38.1 (pl. 37, with description on p. 55).

²⁹ Dressel, *Medaillone*, pp. 62f. (no. 31, Diva Faustina I: "Rötliche Bronze. [...] von einem breiten, beiderseits sehr schön profilierten Messingrahmen umgeben"). See also Dressel p. 134: "Die Prägung des Medaillons aus zwei Metallen beginnt erst um die Mitte des 2. Jahrh.", with note 3, as well as Gnechi, *medaglioni*, vol. 1, p. XLIII: "Ci appaiono i primi esemplari di questa più complicata fabbricazione sotto L. Vero e Lucilla". The Vienna specimen of the medallion type L. Verus, Gnechi no. 36 (dated AD 161/162) must, however, be deleted from the list of the earliest bimetallic medallions: this piece (inv. no. MK 32149: 32.45 g ; 1 h) was erroneously catalogued as being of "Zweierlei Bronze" by W. Kubitschek, *Ausgewählte römische Medaillons der kaiserlichen Münzensammlung in Wien* (Vienna, 1909), p. 6, no. 46 (with illustration on pl. 3), and Gnechi apparently simply followed suit.

³⁰ Dressel, *Medaillone*, p. 135. See also Toynbee, *Medallions* pp. 17f. for the date range Antoninus Pius – Diocletian.

³¹ R. Göbl, *Antike Numismatik*, 2 vols (Munich, 1978), no. 307 (pl. 27).

³² MacDowall, *WCN* 274.

³³ Göbl quoted the piece from Cahn 68 (26 Nov. 1930: Simon coll.), 257 ("auf Dupondienflan"). It had previously been offered in Cahn 61 (3 Dec. 1928: Hahn coll.), 776 ("Kleines Medaillon auf dickem Schrötling") and resurfaced subsequently in A. Canessa – L. De Nicola, *Listino Speciale*, Dec. 1950, 180 ("Contorniato"). It is the piece Mittag, *Medaillons*, no. Nero 5.

³⁴ Göbl vol. 2, p. 141, no. 307: "Münzprobe (Prunkabschlag)"; "Zwei Metalle (Ring: Kupfer?). Die Verwendung zweier Metalle (*de deux cuivres*) ist für Münzproben unüblich und ist vornehmlich in der Medaillontechnik des 2. Jh. n. Chr. geläufig."; "zwei Metalle im Katalog nicht erkannt".

³⁵ Compare the material collected by Mittag, *Medaillons*, plates 9–12, and his discussion on pp. 34–6. Nearly all the Neronian "pseudo-medallions" known to him were manufactured at the mint of Rome.

dies were struck on impressively large flans with diameters of *c.*45–55 mm, which were then frequently grooved with decorative concentric rims made by a lathe (see, e.g., **Pls 11–12, 8–10**).³⁶ The sporadic use of *dupondius* dies for such spectacular “pseudo-medallions” is also attested (e.g. **Pl. 12, 11**). One “presentation piece” from the mint of Rome on a considerably smaller, but still oversized flan made of orichalcum even features the type used on the *as* discussed here, the emperor’s Genius (**Pl. 12, 12**).³⁷ Furthermore, a strike of *as*-dies on a particularly thick flan is attested (**Pl. 12, 13**). Normally, the flans for pieces of that kind were monometallic, but one large piece struck from *sestertius* dies which was repeatedly offered for sale between 2007 and 2010³⁸ seems to be different (**Pl. 12, 14**): on its latest appearance, it was labelled “bimetallic medallion” in the auction catalogue.³⁹ The reason for this may be revealed by careful examination of the image available: in the middle of the obverse field, somewhat displaced to the right, a slightly irregular line encircling Nero’s face (without forming a perfectly rounded circle in itself) is clearly visible. Similarly, a line of the same sort, though less distinct, may be discerned right in the centre of the reverse. If the cataloguer was correct in identifying the piece as bimetallic, one might suppose that the flan of the piece consists of an orichalcum disc with a rather small copper core. Though the shape of the line on the obverse is very reminiscent of the shape of the “crater” on the obverse of our *as*, the production technique of the two flans would have been completely different, since in the case of the *sestertius* the central inlay would go through the entire coin.

The newly discovered piece can thus perhaps be put in the context of other experiments which the Roman mint under Nero conducted, using composite orichalcum/copper flans in order to create visually striking “proto-medallions”. The prototype flans that were tested may have included both pieces with a small solid inlaid core and pieces with central surface inlays. The damage on our *as* vividly demonstrates why, in the long run, the technique used for it could not prevail: flans with solid cores were simply more durable.

We cannot tell exactly where the inspiration to try out the production of bimetallic coins or medals came from: there do not seem to be obvious precursors for this technique in any Greek coinage. A civic coin of Apamea in Phrygia of the 50s BC

The two pieces in the Vienna collection illustrated by A. Alföldi, *Die Kontorniaten. Ein verkanntes Propagandamittel der stadtrömischen heidnischen Aristokratie in ihrem Kampfe gegen das christliche Kaisertum* (Budapest – Leipzig, 1943), pl. XLVIII, nos. 10–11 (not catalogued by Mittag) are probably early modern casts (KHM Vienna, inv. no. MK 32.509–32.510: 54.34 g; 6 h – 61.14 g; 5 h).

³⁶ The fact that these spectacular pieces seem to have been forged since the Renaissance makes it especially difficult to deal with this class of material today.

³⁷ 16.59 g; 6 h, max. diameter 30 mm. Ben Lee Damsky collection, on deposit at the Yale University Art Gallery. Ex CNG Electronic Auction 170 (8 Aug. 2007), 209 (= Electronic Auction 100, 27 Oct. 2004, 145). The obv. legend is probably NERO CLAVD CAESAR AVG GERM P M TR P IMP P P, the type consequently *RIC* 217 (= MacDowall, *WCN* 267).

³⁸ Mittag, *Medaillons*, no. Nero 8. Giessener Münzhandlung Gorny & Mosch 159 (8 Oct. 2007), 379 (64.80 g) = Baldwin’s 62 (29 Sept. 2009), 84 (64.81 g) = The New York Sale (Baldwin’s – Markov – M&M) 23 (6 Jan. 2010), 137 (64.80 g). Reverse: Roma seated left; *RIC* 273; MacDowall, *WCN* 145.

³⁹ This is accepted by Mittag, *Medaillons*, p. 126 (“bimetallich”), who thus implicitly contradicts his assertion about the first occurrence of bimetallic pieces under Galba on p. 18.

(London: *BMC* 52) struck on a large orichalum flan with a grooved edge, which exhibits a contemporary silver plating in the centre of its obverse, is about the closest analogy at hand, although it is not clear whether the plating was applied to this coin at the mint itself, nor which technique was used. Concerning the occasion on which the bimetallic copper/orichalum pieces were invented in Rome, the *aes* reform of Nero with its (temporary) introduction of a general orichalum coinage in AD 64⁴⁰ may have triggered experiments with the two metals on the part of workmen in the mint. At first glance one might suspect that the copper inlay of the *as* presented here was the flattened flan of a small copper *quadrans* from the workshop. This suggestion must, however, be discarded in view of that fact that our coin was struck in the second phase of Nero's general orichalum coinage as reconstructed by MacDowall (issue III overall),⁴¹ which was characterized not only by the re-introduction of the SC and the addition of value marks, but also by the use of the yellowish alloy for the entire denominational range, including *quadrantes*. In the preceding issue (MacDowall II), orichalum had been used for this denomination as well. It was only in the subsequent group (MacDowall IV) that the mint reverted to copper for the smallest coins then produced. This means that the copper inlay cannot have been manufactured from the flan of a copper *quadrans*, since such coins were not at that time in production.

The creativity of Nero's mint-masters in the use of flans with a composite structure, which were apparently unknown before then, is entirely consonant with their other innovative experiments in the manufacture of unusual numismatic items. Several classes of objects may be distinguished.

First, there is some evidence for the occasional production of uniface pieces in bronze under Nero, often referred to as "patterns" or "trial strikes".⁴² Such objects are not attested before Nero's rule.⁴³ A specimen in the British Museum is from a *dupondius* obverse die of the mint of Rome struck on a thick *sestertius* flan of orichalum (29.54 g) and has a completely blank reverse (**Pl. 13, 15**).⁴⁴ A *sestertius* in trade, likewise from the mint of Rome, which features hammered edges, also lacks a reverse design (**Pl. 13, 16**). Its weight of 23.74 g may suggest that the reverse has not been tampered with, whereas a rather light *sestertius* with a blank reverse recently offered for sale probably had its design removed after it had left the mint.⁴⁵ A remarkable piece in Munich which was struck from a *sestertius* die (31.81 g: **Pl. 13, 17**) shows some exceptional technical characteristics: it has a circular indentation around the obverse, and to judge from the appearance of the obverse it looks as if a

⁴⁰ For the reform, see MacDowall, *WCN*, pp. 144–9.

⁴¹ *WCN*, p. 75.

⁴² For these phenomena, see in general F. Gneecchi, 'Appunti di numismatica romana LXXI. I medaglioni unilaterali', *RIN* 18 (1905), pp. 421–424; F. Gneecchi, 'Appunti di numismatica romana LXXXI. Bronzi unilaterali e prove di conio', *RIN* 20 (1907), pp. 32–47. The distinction between the two classes of objects Gneecchi mentions in the latter paper's title is often hard to draw; for him, pieces not struck on oversize flans were simple "prove di conio".

⁴³ See the (incomplete) listing of Neronian pieces of this kind provided by MacDowall, *WCN*, p. 206. For illustrations, see also Gneecchi, 'Bronzi unilaterali', pl. 2, nos. 1 (from a *sestertius* die, Pansa coll.) and 6.

⁴⁴ The piece was originally in the collection of L.A. Lawrence and was acquired by the museum only in 1934; it is therefore not listed in *BMCRE* 1. It is illustrated by MacDowall, *WCN*, pl. 22, no. q.

⁴⁵ CNG Electronic Auction 109 (2 Mar. 2005), 205 (19.92 g): "reverse removed".

metal rim was added to the edge, although the alloys used are unclear.⁴⁶ As for the uniface *sestertius* featured in an auction of Otto Helbing Nachf. (24 Oct. 1927, no. 3429: **Pl. 13, 18**), its weight would doubtless be acceptable (24.6 g), but since its reverse is not illustrated in the auction catalogue, it must be treated with caution.⁴⁷ Still, we may conclude that the one-sided strikes of Nero's time were important early precursors of the medallions on heavy flans without a reverse design, which were produced from Trajan onward.⁴⁸

Second, there are *asses* from Nero's reign which were struck by coupling two obverse dies. Such "double-headed" coins, as well as complementary "double-tailed" pieces of the same denomination, are attested until Commodus, with a first peak in their incidence observable under Trajan.⁴⁹ This class of hybrid coins, the purpose of which still is not completely clear,⁵⁰ was first studied more than a century ago by Robert Mowat.⁵¹ The earliest "double-headed" *as* which he was able to illustrate was Neronian,⁵² and a piece of this kind produced under Nero is still the earliest that we can document today (**Pl. 13, 19**), although the existence of early modern cast forgeries contaminates the evidence (**Pl. 13, 20**).⁵³ It is of course possible that isolated "double-headed" precursors from an earlier period will some day come to light, since a Tiberian piece of this class was reported as being in Queen Christina's collection by Sigebert Havercamp in 1742.⁵⁴ Nevertheless, the authenticity of this

⁴⁶ The reverse is not completely blank, but has traces of a border of dots. This specimen was illustrated by Alföldi, *Kontorniaten*, pl. XLVIII, no. 13.

⁴⁷ MacDowall, *WCN*, p. 206, also reports a uniface *sestertius* trial strike in the Vatican Museum (no weight given).

⁴⁸ Woytek, *Traianus*, nos 920–1 (with the commentary *ad loc.* as well as in vol. 1, p. 170f.) = Mittag, *Medaillons*, nos Tra 1 and Tra 16. Mittag no. Tra 15 shows in fact a portrait of Sabina (see Woytek, *Traianus*, p. 538).

⁴⁹ Woytek, *Traianus*, nos 901[H]–913[H].

⁵⁰ See the detailed commentary (with further bibliographical references) in Woytek, *Traianus*, pp. 169f. Perhaps these pieces were produced from older dies in order to use them up.

⁵¹ R. Mowat, 'Les essais monétaires de répétition et la division du travail', *RN*, 4^{ème} série, 6 (1902), pp. 179–202.

⁵² See Mowat, 'essais', p. 192, no. 12 and pl. VI, no. 1 (probably the piece from his own collection; see the entry on p. 192: "Collection Mowat"). Mowat (*ibid.*) also refers to a similar piece in the Paris collection: ("Cabinet de France, m[o]yen. b[ronze]., 4859"); this *as*, which *BMCRE* I, p. 247 * cites as well, was not, however, catalogued by Giard in *BNCMER* II.

⁵³ For the ANS specimen at **Pl. 13, 19**, see MacDowall, *WCN*, p. 180, note 2. It is from the same dies as (but not identical with) the coin illustrated by Mowat. The holed piece in Vienna from the Tiepolo collection (**Pl. 13, 20**; also same dies) is in all probability a modern cast, as is another specimen in the Viennese coin cabinet (inv. no. MK 70028: 11.08 g, 12 h).

⁵⁴ *Nummophylacium Reginae Christinae, Quod Comprehendit Numismata Aerea Imperatorum Romanorum, Latina, Graeca, atque in Coloniis Cusa, Quondam A Petro Santes Bartolo, Summo Artificio Summaque Fide Incisa Tabulis Aeneis LXIII* (Hagae Comitum, 1742), pl. 47 and p. 305 (nos 29–30). See also *Thesauri Morelliani Tomus Primus, Sive Christ. Schlegelii, Sigeb. Haverkampii, & Antonii Francisci Gorii Commentaria In XII. Priorum Imperatorum Romanorum Numismata Aurea, Argentea, & Aerea, Cujuscunque Moduli, diligentissime conquisita, & ad ipsos Nummos accuratissime delineata, a Celeberrimo Antiquario Andrea Morellio*. [...] (Amstelaedami, 1752), p. 596, nos 5–6 and the corresponding plate in vol. 3 ("Tab. VII"), where the same coin is illustrated: it had already been included in his collection of engravings by André Morell (1646–1703). This type, which was also listed by Cohen (vol. 1, second edition, Tibère, 43; with location "F", i. e. Paris, probably in error) corresponds to Mowat, 'essais', p. 192, no. 11.

coin cannot be ascertained at the moment, and even if it turns out to be genuine, the (more or less) unbroken sequence of “two-headed” *asses* still started only with Nero. As for “double-tailed” *asses*, a piece in the Vienna Coin Cabinet featuring Victory flying left with a shield on both sides, a classic Neronian reverse (*RIC* 312ff. etc.), might indicate that this class of coins started to be produced under Nero as well, if the specimen is genuine (**Pl. 13, 21**).

Third, an oddity (**Pl. 13, 22**). In the collection of the British Museum,⁵⁵ there is a copper *as* of uncertain reverse type which featured the head of Nero to the right on its obverse; the remains of the obverse legend NERO CLAVD CAESAR AVG G[are still visible. This piece was overstruck with two dies of different sizes⁵⁶: the obverse with a GENIO AVGVSTI reverse die without SC, which was appropriate for the denomination, whereas a small *semis* obverse die was used to overstrike the reverse. It shows Nero’s bare head r., encircled by the legend NERO CLAVDIVS CAESAR AVG GERM PM TR PPP; *semisses* of this type are dated to AD 62 by MacDowall.⁵⁷ The only vague parallels to this piece are provided by *sestertii* of Vespasian from the mint of Rome which were struck in AD 71 from an obverse die significantly smaller than the reverse die. This die, which is the size of an *as* die, but is not attested for this denomination, bears the legend IMP CAESAR VESPASIAN AVG P M TR POT P P COS III and was coupled with five reverse dies of four different types.⁵⁸

Finally, mention must be made in this context of mirror-cases which incorporate bronze coins of Nero. These unusual paranumismatic objects were surveyed in the 1990s in no fewer than three systematic studies.⁵⁹ In order to manufacture the class of mirrors which interests us here,⁶⁰ the coins – usually *sestertii*, though *dupondii* are attested as well⁶¹ – were cut lengthwise so that obverse and reverse were separated; the two halves of the coins were then normally affixed to (or integrated in) the centres of the two bronze parts of a box mirror which had elaborate concentric decorative grooving.⁶² The appearance of such box mirrors, when closed, was thus very similar

⁵⁵ *BMCRE* 1, Nero 372 (with note); 14.93 g.

⁵⁶ See the discussion of the overstrike by MacDowall, *WCN*, pp. 45f. and the illustration pl. 22, no. n. According to MacDowall (pp. 45 and 206), a parallel piece is kept in Stockholm.

⁵⁷ MacDowall, *WCN*, pp. 182 and 206.

⁵⁸ *RIC* 2.1² Vespasian 137–40. See *BMCRE* 2, 767; *BNCMER* 3, 544; CNG 50 (23 June 1999), 78 and 79 (Vermeule coll.); R. Witschonke – P. van Alfen (eds), *One Hundred Years of Solitude. Collecting by the New York Numismatic Club* (New York, n. d. [2008]), p. 10, nos. B30–B31.

⁵⁹ P.F. Mittag, ‘Die Münzsammlung des Römisch-Germanischen Museums Köln’, *Kölner Jahrbuch* 30 (1997), pp. 181–223, esp. 190–6 (see also Mittag, *Medaillons*, p. 35); K. Dahmen, ‘Ein Loblied auf den schönen Kaiser. Zur möglichen Deutung der mit Nero-Münzen verzierten römischen Dosenspiegel’, *Arch. Anz. DAI* 1998, pp. 319–45; P.-A. Besombes, ‘Les miroirs de Néron’, *RN* 153 (1998), pp. 119–40.

⁶⁰ For a detailed typology, see Mittag, ‘Münzsammlung’, p. 191, and Dahmen, ‘Loblied’, pp. 320f., whom we follow here. For a different – and rather implausible – view, see Besombes, ‘miroirs’, pp. 121f.

⁶¹ Dahmen, ‘Loblied’, pp. 321 and 325, fig. 6.

⁶² In a few cases, there is no large rim, and the coins were directly hollowed out to house the mirrors, or perhaps rather to be tinned or silvered themselves in order to function as mirrors: see Dahmen, ‘Loblied’, pp. 320f., and esp. Besombes, ‘miroirs’, pp. 136–40 and pl. 16f. Fragments of such pieces, usually hollowed-out obverses, are sometimes offered for sale, e.g. Münz Zentrum 38 (16 Apr. 1980), 79 (14.05 g); Sternberg 13 (17 Nov. 1983), 586 (6.29 g); NAC O (13 May 2004), 1922 (9.24 g); CNG Electronic Auction 170 (8 Aug. 2007), 211 (6.98 g); Giessener Münzhandlung 191 (11 Oct. 2010), 2709

to Neronian “pseudo-medallions” struck on large flans (see **Pl. 13, 23**). Since these objects are almost exclusively decorated with Neronian coins, a special reason for their appearance may be postulated. In view of the fact that the coins used for them were nearly all struck in Lugdunum⁶³ and find-spots of the objects concentrate in the north-western provinces of the Roman Empire,⁶⁴ production in the west can be surmised, and indeed Lugdunum itself has been proposed.⁶⁵ Scholars do not, however, agree as to the environment in which these mirrors originated: whereas Peter Mittag hypothesizes that they may have been manufactured in large numbers by the imperial mint itself (or a closely associated enterprise) in order to be distributed among Roman soldiers of the armies stationed on the northwestern frontier of the empire,⁶⁶ Karsten Dahmen prefers to view them not as official products, but as objects made in private workshops for domestic use.⁶⁷ Paul-André Besombes, for his part, agrees with Mittag in regarding the mirrors as official products. He presumes that they fulfilled ceremonial functions, much like Roman medallions, but, unlike Mittag, does not rule out their production in Italy (Rome).⁶⁸ This seems unlikely: the very fact that there are, by and large, two geographically well-defined complementary groups of similar ‘ceremonial’ objects, *viz.* framed box mirrors featuring coins from the mint of Lugdunum and large “proto-medallions” from the mint of Rome, lends plausibility to the view that these groups of items were used by the state for similar purposes in different areas of the empire and were possibly intended for different social groups.⁶⁹

To conclude, the role of Nero as one of the trailblazers of Roman imperial medallion production had in principle already been recognized by Toynbee⁷⁰ and Mittag.⁷¹ Until now, however, he was regarded as such mainly on the basis of the few strikes from *sestertius* dies on ostentatiously-decorated large flans which have come down to us. But the remarkably creative Roman mint of Neronian times can also be shown to have experimented in several other ways with the artistic possibilities that metalwork and coin production offered: the evidence presented here seems to indicate that this included the invention of bimetallic presentation pieces on composite copper and orichalcum flans, whose heyday as vehicles of imperial (self-)representation was to come only more than one hundred years later.

(8.60 g); DNW (Dix, Noonan, Webb) 28 Sept. 2010 (Catalogue A9), 723 (8.71 g). Intact mirrors of this type rarely turn up in trade; see, however, Giessener Münzhandlung 160 (8 Oct. 2007), 2865 (25.36 g). For a comparable piece from a later period, see S. Heath, ‘A box mirror made from two Antinous medallions of Smyrna’, *AJN* Second Series 18 (2006), pp. 63–74; see esp. 64f. for a detailed analysis of the production technique employed.

⁶³ Dahmen, ‘Loblied’, p. 321.

⁶⁴ Mittag, ‘Münzsammlung’, p. 195 (with map of distribution); Dahmen, ‘Loblied’, p. 328.

⁶⁵ Mittag, ‘Münzsammlung’, p. 195; Dahmen, ‘Loblied’, p. 329.

⁶⁶ Mittag, ‘Münzsammlung’, pp. 195f. (production “in der Münzstätte in Lyon selbst oder in einem nachgeordneten Betrieb”).

⁶⁷ Dahmen, ‘Loblied’, p. 331f. According to him, these objects reflect the loyalty and gratitude of the citizens of Lugdunum toward Nero (330f.).

⁶⁸ Besombes, ‘miroirs’, pp. 123, 125 and 128.

⁶⁹ See Mittag, *Medaillons*, p. 35.

⁷⁰ Toynbee, *Medallions*, p. 26.

⁷¹ Mittag, *Medaillons*, pp. 34f.

List of illustrations on Plates 10-13

- 1 Nero, *as*, Rome, *RIC* 1, 215. Private coll. (7.05 g, 6 h. Fragmented, holed.)
- 1a As 1, 200%.
- 2 Nero, *as*, Rome, *RIC* 1, 215. ANS 1892.32.1 (8.55 g, 6 h)
- 3 Nero, *as*, Rome, *RIC* 1, 215. *Ars Classica* 17 (3 Oct. 1934: Sir Arthur J. Evans et al.), no. 1275 (8.78 g)
- 4 Nero, *dupondius*, Lugdunum, *RIC* 1, 376. Cambridge, Fitzwilliam Museum, CM 1497-1963 (16.42g, 6 h). c/m “SPQR” (Martini, *Pangerl* 27).
- 5 Trajan, *sestertius* on bimetallic flan, Rome, *MIR* 203cB. *RIN* 82 (1980), pp. 229–30 (23.7 g)
- 6 Caracalla, *sestertius* on bimetallic flan, Rome, *RIC* 4,1, 500b. British Museum 1981,0412.1 (33.81 g, 12 h)
- 7 Nero, *as* on large flan, Rome, *RIC* 1, 206. Cahn 61 (3 Dec. 1928: Hahn coll.), no. 776
- 8 Nero, *sestertius* on large flan, Rome, *RIC* 1, 139. British Museum 1844,1008.20 (88.54 g, 6 h)
- 9 Nero, *sestertius* on large flan, Rome, *RIC* 1, 270. Vienna, KHM MK 5660 (69.40 g, 6 h)
- 10 Nero, *sestertius* on large flan, Rome *RIC* 1, 333f. var. (with *aegis*: bust C). Staatliche Museen zu Berlin, Münzkabinett, acc. 1846/7041 (79.72 g, 7 h. Two holes, one of them with remains of iron nail.) <<http://www.smb.museum/ikmk>>
- 11 Nero, *dupondius* on large flan, Lugdunum, *RIC* 1, 522. British Museum 1844,1008.18 (51.40 g, 8 h)
- 12 Nero, *as* on large flan, Rome, *RIC* 1, 217. Ben Lee Damsky coll., Yale University Art Gallery (16.59 g, 6 h)
- 13 Nero, *as* on thick flan, Rome, *RIC* 1, 307. Oxford, Ashmolean Museum, ex Christie’s 30 May 1949 (Fitzwilliam), no. 375 (29.48 g, 6 h)
- 14 Nero, *sestertius* on large (bimetallic?) flan, Rome, *RIC* 1, 273. The New York Sale 23 (6 Jan. 2010), no. 137 (64.80 g)
- 15 Nero, uniface strike on *sestertius* flan (but *dupondius* die), Rome. British Museum 1934,1018.2 (29.54 g)
- 16 Nero, uniface strike on *sestertius* flan, Rome. Münz Zentrum 38 (16 April 1980), no. 78 (23.74 g, hammered edges)
- 17 Nero, strike on *sestertius* flan without reverse design, Rome. Munich, Staatliche Münzsammlung (31.81 g)
- 18 Nero, uniface strike on *sestertius* flan. Otto Helbing Nachf. (24 Oct. 1927), no. 3429 (24.6 g)
- 19 Nero, two-headed *as*, Rome. ANS 1944.100.39766 (10.06 g, 6 h)
- 20 Nero, two-headed *as*. Modern cast. Vienna, KHM MK 5734 (9.13 g, 6h. Holed.)
- 21 Nero, two-tailed *as*. Vienna, KHM MK 70025 (9.88 g, 5 h)
- 22 Nero, *as*, Rome (overstruck). British Museum, *BMCRE* 1, Nero 372 (14.93 g, 6 h)
- 23 Box-mirror featuring *dupondius* of Nero, Lugdunum, *RIC* 1, 519. The Bru Sale 1 (19 June 2010), no. 56 (64.50 g)

PLATE 10

SCHINDEL and WOYTEK,
NERO AND THE MAKING OF THE ROMAN MEDALLION (1)

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SCHINDEL and WOYTEK,
NERO AND THE MAKING OF THE ROMAN MEDALLION (2)

PLATE 12

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SCHINDEL and WOYTEK,
NERO AND THE MAKING OF THE ROMAN MEDALLION (3)

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